

In-Slice Management Decomposition and Implementation Issues

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Abstract—Network slicing management and orchestration typically use centralised OSS/BSS combined with ETSI MANO orchestrator. In [6] it has been proposed the In-Slice Management (ISM) concept in which network slicing system management is autonomic, distributed, and slice management is a part of the Network Slice (NS). There were published several papers that explored this topic. Still, none provided implementation details and issues related to unified NS reconfiguration, including NS run-time orchestration combined with classical management and the impact of NS reconfiguration on IMS components. The paper addresses these issues by defining ISM services and proposing, common for all ISM services, cooperative monitoring and actuating sublayers to handle reconfigurations smoothly. The mutual impact of ISM management services responsible for performance, fault, and security management is also addressed. The presented concept can be a basis for a generic ISM template that can be adapted to many NS types with marginal efforts.

Index Terms—5G, 6G, ETSI MANO, network slicing, network virtualization, orchestration, autonomic network management

I. INTRODUCTION

The Network Slices (NSs) enable creation of virtual networks a top of shared infrastructure composed of typically virtualised resources (computing, storage, and connectivity). The solution comes with promise of service-aware networks. It provides multiple benefits such as low total cost of ownership, short time to market and efficient use of aggregated infrastructure resources that are shared among multiple NSs. An NS is typically implemented as an ETSI NFV [1], [2] Network Service and uses the ETSI MANO orchestrator. The NS concept is a part of the Standalone version of the 5G network (5G SA) [3], [4]. The ETSI NFV approach has multiple drawbacks, including centralised orchestration and common OSS/BSS for all slices that raise isolation and scalability issues. There is, therefore, a need to look for a new that is free from the mentioned in [5] issues. A new approach to network slicing has already been proposed in [6] detailed in [7] and enhanced in [8]. In this concept, called in the paper In-Slice Management (ISM), the NS management becomes part of the NS template and may send orchestration requests. None of the already published papers provides ISM implementation details and issues related to unified NS reconfiguration, including NS run-time orchestration combined with management and the impact of NS reconfiguration on IMS other components. This paper addresses the issues by defining programmable ISM

services responsible for the performance, fault, and security management. Moreover, there are proposed cooperating monitoring and actuating sublayers that are common for all ISM services. The presented concept can be a basis for a generic ISM template that can be adapted for many NS types with marginal effort. Section 2 will describe the related work, and Section 3 will describe the proposed concept. Finally, Section 4 concludes the paper.

II. RELATED WORK

A survey of approaches to NS and issues can be found in [9]–[11]. Some of them, realised in the framework of the European Research Program H2020, are described in [12]. The ETSI MANO framework is a widely accepted solution for NS [2]. In the framework, the Operation/Business Support System (OSS/BSS) is placed on top of MANO and plays a vital role in the whole ETSI NFV picture. The 3GPP approach to 5G System (5GS) orchestration and management [3], [14], [15] supports NS (at the level of network function, sub-network slice, network slice and communication service management) using ETSI NFV mechanisms. The 3GPP management system architecture is complementary to ETSI NFV MANO [4]. Unfortunately, the functionality of the OSS/BSS had not been fully defined by 3GPP or ETSI; the OSS/BSS centralisation raises scalability and performance issues; NS tenants cannot have a private management system; the common for all slices OSS/BSS system impacts negatively slice isolation and raises serious security concerns, as described in [13] and the OSS/BSS is not programmable. Finally, the lack of proper separation of concerns makes the solution over-complex. Some of the mentioned problems have been addressed in [6]. The concept has added a management plane to each slice (i.e. ISM) and provided a direct slice tenant interface. More details of the idea, inspired by the GANA approach [16] have been provided in [7]. In the autonomous management concept, composed of the control-loops, i.e. following the MAPE (Monitor-Analyze-Plan-Execute) approach, each VNF is autonomous, and each slice has an autonomous Slice Manager and the whole system is managed and orchestrated by the autonomous OSS/BSS (see Fig. 1). The distributed approach provides a good separation of concerns and isolation between slices. Presented In [8], [17], the MonB5G approach defines the AI-driven architecture of the overall NS system with ISM. The ISM, called Slice MonbB5G Layer, comprises the Monitoring

Fig. 1. MonB5G simplified architecture (single slice, single domain) showing distribution of autonomic management functionalities.

Subsystem, multiple Analytic Engines (AEs) and Decision Engines (DEs) that are AI-driven. The ISM of the MonB5G can trigger orchestration. The MonB5G defines the structure of slice MonB5G Layer (i.e. the ISM) but doesn't provide details of NS runtime operations, including orchestration.

III. IN-SLICE MANAGEMENT INTERNAL ARCHITECTURE

In this section, details of ISM decomposition are provided. In the proposed approach, we focus on ISM's management functions and their interactions. In our description, we will follow ETSI NFV; however, the presented approach is generic. We assume that the slice is already deployed. Therefore, the operations related to its deployment and termination will be barely touched only. Moreover, we address single domain operations only, and the presented in [8] approach to multi-domain slicing is also applicable in the presented case. However, a single management domain complexity is still very high, and to cope with it; we propose decomposing ISM into a set of Management Services (MS). To that end, we will use the well-known decomposition of management systems into Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance and Security (FCAPS) components. We will focus on fault, security, and performance management only because these functions trigger configuration changes — the accounting is typically linked with resource consumption and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). All MSs can consume the monitoring information, and the NS configuration can be done by MSs, NS operator and by the Global OSS/BSS. In [8] the slice runtime orchestration driven by ISM can also make NS reconfigurations. We identify, therefore, three generic types of NS reconfiguration mechanisms:

- CPM - NS configuration parameters modification (classical management operation);
- RS - resource scaling, update of resources allocated to virtual functions and links;
- TM - slice topology modification by VNF migration, VNF addition or removal.

We see these three operation types as control knobs that should be used uniformly. Please note that the above-mentioned operations can also be used for ISM reconfiguration or enhancements. In most cases, however, the Slice Functional Layer (see Fig. 1) will be reconfigured.

The NS reconfigurations impact the obtained monitoring data, and TM reconfigurations impact slice topology and, as a result, the way of correlating monitoring data. Moreover, the reconfiguration process in progress has also to be handled adequately by ISM components. These reasons show a need for cooperation between ISM's reconfiguration and monitoring parts. We propose to decompose ISM into Autonomous Monitoring Sublayer (AMS), Intelligent Reconfiguration Sublayer (IRS), Fault Management Service (FMS), Performance Management Service, Security Management Service (SMS) and Auxiliary Management Functions (AMF). The AMS and IRS sublayers are common for all services. The AMS sublayer provides generic and dedicated, programmable monitoring, and the IRS is responsible for synchronising and executing operations related to NS reconfigurations. The list of management services can be enhanced, and each service can be reprogrammed by itself or by the Global OSS/BSS. It is assumed that ISM uses a message bus for interaction between components. The functionalities of ISM components and their interactions are described in subsequent subsections.

A. Autonomous Monitoring Sublayer (AMS)

AMS is a sublayer that is used by all Management Services (MS) in order to obtain information about NS status and the status of the Infrastructure. It collects information from all sources (VNFs, Infrastructure) and processes the received data. Data processing includes data aggregation, filtering, interpolation and collecting alerts. The processing includes topology-dependent data processing regarding data flows. Following GANA, VNFs are self-managed, so they can expose to AMS preprocessed monitoring information. The AMF has a database that keeps all the monitoring information (Monitoring Database, MDB) and NS topology (Topology Database, TDB). ISM's other components may subscribe to AMS information using the message bus mechanism. It is assumed that AMS provides a generic monitoring service that is adaptive and customisable to a certain extent. The adaptiveness means that AMS analysing the monitoring data can change data sample rate, etc. The customisation means that some components can be dynamically added to AMS if MS needs them. In the case of FMS, such entities can be anomaly detection engines; in the case of PMS, the entities may calculate and predict NS KPIs; in the case of SMS, they can be engines dedicated to monitoring specific attack types. The AMS output is consumed not only by MSs but also by IRS to verify the results of reconfiguration, system stability, and take autonomous decisions about reactive resource scaling. The AMS is not only responsible for collecting monitoring data but also makes predictions and exposes them similarly to NWDAF [18], [19]. As we will explain later, the monitoring has to be synchronised with the NS reconfiguration process

Fig. 2. Overall ISM internal architecture

via a direct interface to IRS to avoid monitoring the transition states and adapt monitoring to NS topology changes.

B. Intelligent Reconfiguration Sublayer (IRS)

The NS reconfiguration can be triggered by MS services, slice operator (tenant), or external, common to all slices OSS/BSS. The IRS puts NS reconfiguration requests into a priority queue. Each reconfiguration request may have the assigned priority by the component that sends it, but yet another priority can also be assigned to each component. The mechanisms can be used, for example, for providing a higher priority to FMS and SMS than to PMS-driven reconfigurations. Please note that such a mechanism is not the ultimate solution for finding the best system configuration driven by different, multiple, single-objective optimisation functions. The problem has been described in [20], and the detailed analysis of it is out of the scope of the paper. The multi-objective optimisation algorithms can, however, be implemented as a part of the IRS engine. The IRS provides a kind of abstraction and accepts intent-like reconfiguration requests and needs; therefore, an entity responsible for the intent conversion into a set of ordered, atomic commands sent to NS components (VNFs) and/or to the orchestrator. As we mentioned, we differentiate three types of reconfigurations. The change of parameters of the deployed slice is a relatively simple procedure. The resource scaling may be driven because of two reasons. The first one is reactive and is based on observing the level of consumed resources. The second, proactive one, often called data-driven, lies in resource allocation based on the observation of NS-related data, KPIs trends, etc. The reactive resource allocation concerns nodes (VNFs), not services. In the proposed approach, the reactive resource allocation is made autonomously by IRS based on the information obtained from AMS. The NS template change, i.e. migrating, adding or

removing VNFs, involves orchestration. To handle such a case, IRS interacts with the NFVO triggering the operation. Each old and new reconfiguration is stored in the Reconfiguration Database (RDB). During reconfiguration, the AMS and all MSs are informed that a reconfiguration is in progress, as it may cause a change in the monitoring values and how they are calculated. Each reconfiguration has to be confirmed, and the reconfiguration in progress can disturb monitoring data. Therefore, all the components of AMS, including those dedicated to MS anomaly detection engines (AEs) and KPI calculation engines, are informed about the progressing reconfiguration to avoid unnecessary detection of anomalies and mistaken KPIs calculation. Until the reconfiguration is completed, they should keep the values before the reconfiguration has started. The change of NS parameters or resource scaling are typically fast operations (system reactions are within seconds). Still, modifying topology (adding/removing a VNF) and redirecting traffic is an operation that may take some time (in order of minutes). The time depends on the virtualisation technology (virtual machines or containers). Despite the fact that the process takes time, its enforcement has to be quick in order to preserve connectivity or service continuity. To speed up this process, it is possible to integrate the additional VNFs in the template but bypass them until they are needed. The price of the approach is a bigger NS template footprint. The slice tenant or system operator can control the IRS operations using policies, but, in contrast to AMS, we don't see a need to modify IRS functionalities using orchestration.

C. ISM services

ISM Management Services (MS) are functions that implement specific management goals. Their architecture is similar, but the roles of components and the algorithms used are different. All the services must interact with AMS to obtain

information about NS and with IRS to enforce the new configuration. Each MS may require a dedicated monitoring component installed in AMS. Such components can be a part of the NS template or dynamically added during slice run-time. In the case of PMS, it may calculate KPIs; in the case of FMS, it handles anomaly detection, etc. Installation of such components in AMS is justified by their interactions with AMS, MSs and with IRS to check the result of the reconfiguration and eventually restore the previous configuration. Each MS consist of one or more Decision Engines (DEs), i.e. entities based on the monitoring data obtained from AMS and policy rules defined by slice tenant to define a new NS configuration. Such combined DEs of an MS can be seen as service orchestrators. According to the recent trends, AI algorithms are used for DEs. In the presented in the paper approach, the reconfiguration decision is complex, as the MS has to select which one of the three already described reconfiguration mechanisms should be used in a specific context. It seems that the design of a single algorithm, which can decide if the reconfiguration should be done by changing NS parameters, scaling virtual resources or adding or removing VNFs, can be challenging. To solve the problem, we propose to use a dedicated DE for each reconfiguration type and, atop of such DEs, a master service DE which decides which reconfiguration option should be used. The behaviour of the DEs is following:

- DE responsible for RS. The proactive resource scaling DE functionality of any MS seems relatively simple. The DE has to analyse the NS traffic trends, the number of NS users and, on that basis, decide about the resource scaling in a proactive way, i.e. before the change in resource consumption is noticed. The prediction of future KPIs should also be used. The resource scaling involves the orchestrator. The mechanism is typically used for performance control, and the DE algorithm has to know the mapping between resources allocation and performance indicators. Such mapping can be learned using AI. This mechanism has a marginal impact on the operations of ISM; the new resource allocation simply must be stored in the reconfiguration database. The process is generally quick and, during enforcement, causes no degradation of PIs. However, the new resource allocation may trigger CPM reconfiguration, for example, to provide better load balancing. The performance optimisation procedure can be independent and use the CPM mechanism.
- DE responsible for CPM. The change of NS parameters can impact, for example, traffic flows by using the load balancing mechanism or allocating users to radio nodes. This operation is a classical management operation; it doesn't involve the orchestrator and is done relatively quickly. The NS topology is not changed, but the traffic matrix can be impacted; therefore, all IMS entities involved in path monitoring should be aware of the new flow-to-path assignment. It means that AMS functions related to correlation of data, MS analytic engines and the reconfiguration database should be updated.

- DE responsible for TM. The decision about the topology change by adding, removing or migrating VNF is typically based on the analysis of the present NS topology, matrix of traffic flows and the load of each VNF. It can be enforced by PMS, typically due to users' mobility, by FMS to create a new path with active nodes (VNFs), and by SMS to deploy additional nodes for traffic inspection or blocking. This operation involves orchestration and can be time-consuming; therefore, its preparation phase should not disturb the NS behaviour, and enforcement has to be quick. The topology change requires a traffic redirection and impacts NS monitoring that has to be adapted accordingly. A problem with AMF is that new nodes have no history of measurements; therefore, AMF has to take particular measures to synchronise measurements. In some cases, the DEs of MSs also have to be informed about the topology change. The TM can also concern the ISM.

We describe DEs work in parallel DE and yet another DE, MS master DE, atop of the three selects the best option. Following Mon5G, we see analytic engines and DE as AI-driven. In general, if there is no specific preference (see description below), each MS should start from resource reconfiguration. The next option is to change NS parameters, and finally, a topology update can be used. However, this is to be decided by the master DE of each MS, which takes each of the mentioned DEs decisions and selects the best option. Below we describe in more detail the behaviour of PMS, FMS and SMS components.

1) *Performance Management Service (PMS)*: Performance management realize NS optimization goals that are typically expressed in the form of Performance Indicators (PIs). A subset of them, called Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), are often part of SLA. Performance monitoring is a continuous process, and PIs are periodically calculated by an AMS entity dedicated to PMS. The KPIs can also be predicted, which gives more time for the NS reconfiguration. Such reconfigurations triggered by PMS are typically done in small steps following resource demands. This behaviour should be, however, policy controlled, as larger steps decrease the number of reconfiguration operations but provide less efficient usage of resources. As in the generic case described above, the first mechanism triggered by PMS is typically resource scaling (RS). If it is not triggered in advance by PMS, it will be reactively triggered by the IRS. The change of NS configuration parameters (CPM) is the next NS reconfiguration option, allowing traffic redirection to achieve load balancing, etc. Finally, if a need for topology change has been discovered, the orchestration will be involved in updating the topology. The topology change driven by PMS is rather a rare event, and it is typically based on the change in traffic flow distribution, which can be caused by the mobility of users. A good example is the Follow Me approach [21]. Energy consumption can be one of the PIs; therefore, removal of VNF can be driven by PMS. The NS reconfigurations driven by PMS should have the lowest priority out of the three MS services described in the paper.

TABLE I
OVERALL IMPACT OF RECONFIGURATIONS AND SELECTED EVENTS ON ISM COMPONENTS

Event	Impact on AMS	Impact on IRS	Impact or PMS reaction	Impact or FMS reaction	Impact or SMS reaction
IRS: reconfiguration in progress	monitoring data marked	RDB updated when finished	AEs notified, optionally DEs notified	AEs notified, optionally DEs notified	AEs notified, optionally DEs notified
FMS: fault detected	monitoring data marked	stopping new reconfigurations other than FMS driven		deployment of new AEs, DEs or functional NS components	
SMS: attack detected	monitoring data marked	stopping new PMS driven reconfigurations		AEs notified, optionally DEs notified	deployment of new AEs, DEs or functional NS components
IRS: RS	none	RDB updated	none	none	none
PMS: RS				AEs notified	AEs notified
PMS: CPM	flows to paths update		AEs notified, optionally DEs notified	none	AEs notified, optionally DEs notified
FMS: CPM				none	none
SMS: CPM	TDB and MDB modified			AEs notified, optionally DEs notified	AEs notified, optionally DEs notified
PMS: TM					
FMS: TM					
SMS: TM					

2) *Fault Management Service (FMS)*: The fault management is typically composed of three phases: fault detection, identification of the fault source (root-cause analysis) and fault mitigation. Except for the Infrastructure related issues, in the NS case, the most probable are software-related faults that will impact the behaviour of nodes (VNFs) or protocols. Faults can be directly signalled by alerts or can be detected by using the anomaly detection technique. The alerts are obtained immediately and have to be handled quickly. In contrast, the detection of anomalies is based on an observation of the behaviour of NS over a longer period of time. Any of the mentioned events triggers a procedure that is looking for an understanding of the problem; it includes analysis of the status of allocated to NS resources, reachability of nodes, as well as a list of correct and degraded PIs. In the proposed concept, it is assumed that the generic monitoring part of AMS provides alerts, but proactive detection of faults is done by dedicated to faults analytic engines, which are part of FMS but are placed in AMF. In the absence of alerts or anomaly detection, the FMS takes no action. For detection of the source of the fault, the FMS may need to add to itself and or to AMS another component (using ISM TM mechanism) that is tailored to handle specific faults. Two types of reconfigurations can handle fault mitigation, NS parameters change and topology change. The NS parameter change may include the restart of some functions, whereas the topology change allows for adding functions or links that replace the faulty ones. Another data centre can be used for VNF placement in case of data centre issues. Information about fault detection is sent to AMS, and after fault mitigation, the PMS (a continuous process) optimises the NS performance. Even during fault, the PMS is trying to optimise the NS performance; however, it should be notified about the faulty resources and functions. Such information should be included in the topology database of

AMS. Please note that we don't see the RS mechanism as a part of FMS.

3) *Security Management Service (SMS)*: The SMS detects security threats and in response takes some actions. The SMS behaviour and architecture are similar to anomaly-based fault management - first, the threat has to be detected, second, details of the attack have to be provided, and finally, mitigation has to be found. For the detection of threats, dedicated SMS analytic engines are used. The engines monitor anomalies in the user plane and control plane to detect threats and quickly growing or changing consumption of resources. In the case of DoS or DDoS, the increased number of data flows or fast load growth can be a symptom of an attack. The typical attack on virtualised infrastructure lies in the generation of the on/off intensive traffic to enforce continuous RS actions. In case of an early warning of the attack, additional security functions can be deployed in SMS or AMS in order to find a source of problems (attack type). Additionally, some probes can be installed in certain parts of the functional part of the NS (firewalls, Honey Pots, DPIs, etc.). After detection of the attack, all AMS and MS entities should be informed to avoid their competitive reconfigurations. The attack mitigation phase may include blocking flows, traffic redirection, isolation of functions or nodes, etc. Similarly to FMS, the resource scaling is not used as an SMS mechanism, but the mechanism of PMS can be blocked, and the reactive resource scaling also can be blocked or controlled by SMS. After changing the topology and functions, certain modifications have to be made in the monitoring to address topology changes. Blocked flows, functions, or nodes should be marked in the monitoring database to avoid PMS and FMS reactions. The PMS should stop allocating more resources to handle the malicious traffic, and FMS should not take the blocking of some flows or PI degradation as faults.

The AMF components are used to implement several functions essential for ISM's proper behaviour. The functions enable operator- or tenant-based NS configuration, NS self-configuration after deployment, inter-domain NS operations and Policy Based Management (PBM). The functionalities of these blocks are described in detail in [8]. In the context of the paper, the functions have marginal meaning, and their analysis will be omitted.

E. Impact of reconfigurations of ISM components

The naive MAPE approach assumes the existence of multiple, mutually isolated, control-loop-based functions. In the SON case, the problem of coordination of their outputs (conflict resolution) has been noticed, and some recommendations to solve the problem have been proposed [20]. The issue of the mutual feedback of several control-loop-based functions and the impact on monitoring has been so far ignored. According to the discussion presented in the preceding subsections, we have created a table (Table 1) that shows the overall impact of reconfigurations and events (fault, security attacks) on the AMS and MS. Some reconfigurations touch almost all MSs and all AMS components. The analysis shows that MSs and monitoring entities must react for reconfigurations. This reaction however, can be independent of the AI algorithm used as DE of an MS.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

The autonomic or AI driven management concepts are recently very popular. It is justified by the complexity of management and the ability of AI to achieve management goals relatively quickly. Despite many projects and efforts, autonomic network management deployments are still rare. One of the reasons is the autonomic management complexity. The problem of autonomic management is of premium importance in the case of network slicing, as each slice can be seen as a logical network. A significant number of network slices can't be managed manually. The MonB5G approach tries to simplify the management problem by using multiple management subsystems focused on a specific goal. The goal of the proposed in the paper decomposition of the ISM can be seen as a next step - to find a framework that can be uniformly used for multiple management services. The paper's key finding is pretty complex interactions between different components of ISM in real implementations. We have found that the operation of a single MAPE-driven management function impacts other management functions (services) and the monitoring system. The impact is significant, but it can be handled in a systematic way. An important novelty of the paper is the simultaneous use of management and orchestration for NS runtime reconfigurations. The presented concept can be used for generic ISM templates, which customisation for specific NS should be relatively straightforward.

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